

Original Research

Comparative study of heavy metal-induced oxidative stress responses in *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. and *Cyathus striatus* Willd.

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Abstract

Heavy metal exposure causes reactive oxygen species generation and oxidative stress in nearly all aerobic organisms. Antioxidant enzymes with free radical scavenging properties counter this oxidative stress produced by heavy metals. In this study, the effects of heavy metal-induced oxidative stress on the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including catalase, peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase, have been evaluated in two selected lignicolous fungal strains, *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. and *Cyathus striatus* Willd. The results showed that heavy metals exert toxicity in both fungal strains by affecting the oxidative metabolism, as evidenced by increased production of hydrogen peroxide. An increase in malonaldehyde concentration was observed at a concentration of 100 mg/L of metal ions, indicating that heavy metal exposure causes oxidative damage. To counter the oxidative stress, the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including catalase, peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase, were increased upon exposure to metal ion concentrations. However, a decrease in antioxidant enzyme activity was observed with a further increase in metal ion concentration, which indicates reactive oxygen species-induced oxidative stress. Furthermore, reduced glutathione also plays an important role in the detoxification of heavy metal ions at lower concentrations. Thus, this work suggests that these wood-rot fungi, *S. commune* and *C. striatus*, may have the potential to tolerate and accumulate heavy metals by the effective antioxidant defence mechanism, where catalase, peroxidase, superoxide dismutase, and glutathione may play a significant role in this resistance.

Keywords

Antioxidant responses, Intracellular accumulation, Lignicolous fungi, Metal ions, Reactive oxygen species

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Primerjalna študija odzivov na oksidativni stres, povzročen s težkimi kovinami, pri *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. in *Cyathus striatus* Willd.

Izvleček

Izpostavljenost težkim kovinam povzroča nastajanje reaktivnih kisikovih spojin in oksidativni stres v skoraj vseh aerobnih organizmih. Antioksidativni encimi s sposobnostjo odstranjevanja prostih radikalov preprečujejo oksidativni stres, ki ga povzročajo težke kovine. V tej študiji so bili ocenjeni učinki oksidativnega stresa, ki ga povzročajo težke kovine, na aktivnosti antioksidativnih encimov, vključno s katalazo, peroksidazo in superoksid dismutazo, v dveh izbranih lignikolnih glivnih sevih, *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. in *Cyathus striatus* Willd. Rezultati so pokazali, da težke kovine povzročajo stres v obeh glivnih sevih, saj vplivajo na oksidativni metabolizem, kar dokazuje povečana proizvodnja vodikovega peroksida. Pri koncentraciji 100 mg/l kovinskih ionov je bilo opazno povečanje koncentracije malonaldehida, kar kaže, da izpostavljenost težkim kovinam povzroča oksidativno poškodbo. Da bi se zoperstavile oksidativnemu stresu, se je aktivnost antioksidativnih encimov v glivah, vključno s katalazo, peroksidazo in superoksid dismutazo, povečala. Vendar je bilo pri nadaljnjem povečanju koncentracije kovinskih ionov opazno zmanjšanje aktivnosti antioksidativnih encimov, kar kaže na oksidativni stres, ki ga povzročajo reaktivne kisikove spojine. Poleg tega ima zmanjšana koncentracija glutationa pomembno vlogo tudi pri razstrupljanju kovinskih ionov v nižjih koncentracijah. Ta raziskava torej kaže, da imata lesni glivi *S. commune* in *C. striatus*, potencial za prenašanje in kopičenje težkih kovin z učinkovitim antioksidativnim obrambnim mehanizmom, pri čemer imajo katalaza, peroksidaza, superoksid dismutaza in glutation pomembno vlogo pri tej odpornosti.

Ključne besede

Antioksidativni odzivi, Intracelularna akumulacija, Lignikolne glive, Kovinski ioni, Reaktivne kisikove spojine

Introduction

Heavy metal contamination of the aquatic ecosystem has been a global concern over the past few years. Overexposure to heavy metals from industrial smelting, mining ore, agriculture, burning fossil fuels, etc., has been a serious concern nowadays (Mishra and De, 2024). Heavy metals, including copper, cadmium, lead, strontium, nickel, and arsenic, are harmful to various organisms due to their significant bioaccumulation and potential mutagenic and carcinogenic effects (Mondal et al., 2024a). To combat this persistent issue, bioremediation offers a conventional clean-up technology due to its cost-effectiveness and comparatively low harmful impact on the environment. Remediation of heavy metals using biological entities has emerged as an attractive approach to eliminate these heavy metals, which potentially may be conducted with minimal costs and are eco-friendly. Among the various approaches, the mycoremediation technique has been gaining attention recently due to its eco-friendly, cost-effective, and highly

efficient approach (Koul et al., 2021). Both extracellular adsorption and intracellular accumulation are responsible in fungi for the elimination and uptake of metal ions from contaminated sites (Kumar and Dwivedi, 2021). To broaden the application of this technology, it is crucial to comprehend the microbial defence systems that protect against cellular toxicity caused by heavy metals.

Heavy metals can exert toxicity by multiple mechanisms. For instance, metals can cause oxidative stress by scavenging thiols, such as cysteine and glutathione, which are significant non-enzymatic antioxidants (Georgiou-Siafis and Tsiftoglou, 2023). Certain heavy metal ions integrate into the cytoplasm and induce reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, which impacts the mitochondrial microsome, metabolites, intermediates, and cell organelles. This creates a potent oxidising environment *in vivo* that can block the expression of mRNA, substitute the ligand in the active sites of the enzymes, damage DNA and membranes, cause lipid peroxidation, and ultimately result in apoptosis (Zhang et al., 2015). Additionally, metals may result in physi-

ological stress by producing chemical stressors that trigger the generation of ROS, including H_2O_2 , O_2^- , $\cdot OH$, etc. (Alam and Kataria, 2021). Understanding the antioxidant systems of an organism is crucial to determining the effects of metal exposure, as they are the potential targets of heavy metals.

Heavy metals can cause oxidative stress, which starts the production of ROS and eventually affects the cellular components. To counter this effect, the cellular antioxidant defence system plays an important role by scavenging ROS and maintaining cellular redox balance. The antioxidant system is composed of both enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants. Certain antioxidant enzymes, including Catalase (CAT), Peroxidase (POD), Superoxide dismutase (SOD), and non-enzymatic antioxidants like Glutathione peroxidase (GPx), play an important role in defence against oxidation by sequentially sequestering O_2^- and H_2O_2 (Berni et al. 2019). CAT and POD mainly catalyse the conversion of H_2O_2 into water and oxygen rather than singlet oxygen. SOD dismutates the highly reactive superoxide anion (O_2^-) into H_2O_2 and O_2 (Ighodaro et al., 2018). Additionally, the reduced glutathione (GSH) is an essential component in metal scavenging due to the strong affinity of metals for its thiol (-SH) group and its role as a precursor of phytochelatins (Georgiou-Siafis and Tsiftoglou, 2023). GSH catalyses the reduction of oxidised glutathione (GSSG) back to its active form, GSH. GSH acts as a major antioxidant and is composed of glutamine, glycine, and cysteine. Furthermore, heavy metal-mediated inactivation of enzymatic antioxidants may occur through the substitution of cofactors necessary for enzyme function or through metal interaction with sulfhydryl or other functional groups. Understanding the role of these enzymes in the degradation and adsorption of heavy metals is essential to comprehend the biochemical and molecular mechanisms of the biodegradation process.

Wood-rot fungi typically have large biomass, and some strains are known to uptake and eliminate metal ions from contaminated sites and wastewater (Mondal et al., 2024a; 2024b). However, despite several reports on the ability of these fungi to remove heavy metals, the cellular response of fungi to heavy metal stress remains largely unknown. In this study, two selected wood rot fungi, *Schizophyllum commune* and *Cyathus striatus*, have been investigated for their oxidative stress response under heavy metal stress. These fungi are known for lignin degradation (Asgher et al., 2016; Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2024) and have earlier been reported for the adsorption of certain metal ions (Mondal

et al., 2024b; 2025; Chaudhary and Shukla, 2019). The physiological impacts and oxidative stress responses of heavy metals on these fungal strains are still not reported. The present study aims to ascertain how the antioxidant enzymes function after being exposed to heavy metals. The effect of heavy metals (particularly lead, cadmium, zinc, and strontium) on the enzymatic responses (including CAT, POD, SOD, and GSH) has been investigated to determine the oxidative defence mechanisms.

Material and Methods

Fungal biomass preparation

The fungal specimens were collected from the forest area of Purulia district, West Bengal, India. The fruiting bodies were surface sterilised using 1 % Sodium hypochlorite, followed by rinsing with distilled water, and then inoculated on potato dextrose agar (PDA) petri-plates. The plates were kept at 28 ± 2 °C for 5-6 days for the growth of mycelia. Later, the mycelia were transferred to 100 ml of potato dextrose broth (PDB) medium containing different concentrations of metal ion solution, and incubated in a shaker at 100 rpm for 7 days at 28 ± 2 °C. The concentration (100-500 mg/L) of Pb(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), and Sr(II) was prepared using metal salt precursors, such as $Pb(C_2H_3O_2)_2$, $CdCO_3$, $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, and $Sr(NO_3)_2$. The biomass was harvested after 7 days and disrupted using an ultrasonicator for 3.5 min with an interval of 8 sec at 25 °C with an ice bath (Zhang et al., 2015). The homogenised cell-free extract tissue was obtained after centrifuging the homogenised solution at 4 °C.

Cell lysis and estimation of total protein

The cell lysis was performed using lysis buffer containing Tween 80 (1.5% v/v), Triton X-100 (0.5% v/v), Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide (CTAB) (1% w/v), Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS) (5% w/v) in phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) (Alam and Kataria, 2021). The heavy metal accumulated biomass (0.1 g) was suspended in the detergent solution (1.0 ml) for 30 mins and lysed in an incubator shaker at 100 rpm at 28 ± 2 °C. The disrupted cell lysate was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was collected, and protein content was estimated by Lowry's method for crude samples (Christias et al., 1975). To quantify the total protein, Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) was used as a standard.

Estimation of malonaldehyde (MDA) content

The MDA concentration was determined using homogenised tissue extract (0.5 ml) dissolved in 0.1% (w/v) Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution (Zhang et al., 2016). The mixture was centrifuged for 15 min at 10000 rpm, and 0.5 ml supernatant was added to 0.5% Thiobarbituric acid (TBA) in 20% TCA. The mixture was heated at 90 °C for 30 min, and after cooling, the tubes were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min at room temperature. The absorbance was measured at 532 nm and 600 nm, and the difference in absorbance was calculated as MDA concentration.

Estimation of catalase activity

For estimating CAT activity, a total of 3 mL of reaction mixture was prepared, which consisted of 1 mL H₂O₂ (0.3 % v/v), 1.9 mL potassium phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0), and 0.1 mL of homogenised tissue extract (Alam and Kataria, 2021). A decrease in absorbance per minute at 240 nm was observed due to enzymatic decomposition of H₂O₂. The decrease in absorbance per minute per mg of protein in 1 ml of solution at 240 nm was used to define one unit of enzyme activity.

Estimation of peroxidase activity

The POD activity was determined using a 3 mL reaction mixture solution which contained 1 mL guaiacol (0.2 % v/v), 1 mL H₂O₂ (0.3 % v/v), 0.1 mL of homogenised tissue extract, and 0.9 mL phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0) (Alam and Kataria, 2021). The increase in absorbance at 470 nm per minute per mg of protein in 1 ml of solution was considered to be one unit of enzyme activity.

Estimation of superoxide dismutase activity

The SOD activity was determined by the nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) method (Beauchamp and Fridovich, 1971). The blank contained 0.2 ml phosphate buffer, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin; the test contained 0.1 ml NBT, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin, 0.1 ml tissue extract; the standard contained 0.1 ml phosphate buffer, 0.1 ml NBT, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin; the control contained 0.1 ml phosphate buffer, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin, 0.1 ml tissue extract. The standard tube was without the enzyme (tissue extract), and the control was without the substrate

(NBT). The test tube contained substrate and enzyme, and the blank contained neither substrate nor enzyme. Each set of tubes was kept in an illumination chamber for 20 min. The substrate reacted with superoxide anions generated when riboflavin was illuminated with methionine (electron donor) and produced a blue colour complex, formazan. The SOD in the sample was directly proportional to the decrease in formazan formation. One unit of SOD was defined as a 50% reduction in formazan formation. The specific activity of the enzyme was calculated as U/mg protein.

Estimation of glutathione content

To estimate the GSH content, the mycelial extract was prepared by homogenising 0.1 g of mycelia with 1.0 ml of 5% (v/v) sulfosalicylic acid containing 0.1% (v/v) Triton X solution and 1 mM Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). The mixture was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was used for GSH estimation using the sulfhydryl reagent 5,5'-dithio-bis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB). The supernatant (0.5 ml) was mixed with 0.5 ml of 3 mM DTNB and 2.0 ml reaction buffer and kept at room temperature for 10 min. Later, the absorbance was measured at 412 nm for the determination of GSH. The same reaction mixture was supplemented with β-NADPH (0.2 mM) and glutathione reductase (0.1 U mL⁻¹), and a yellow colour derivative, 5'-thio-2-nitrobenzoic acid (TNB), was formed (Huang et al., 2017). The absorbance was measured at 412 nm for the determination of total glutathione. The GSSG was measured from the difference between total glutathione and GSH.

Statistical analysis

All the experiments were carried out in triplicate. The experimental data were given as the mean ± Standard deviation (SD). The results were analysed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS v18.0. A value of P < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Tolerance of fungal biomass to metal ions

The molecular characterisation of fungal specimens was earlier performed based on ITS rRNA sequencing (Mondal et al., 2024b; 2025). The sequences were deposited in

the NCBI GenBank database (Accession no. PP947802 for *Cyathus striatus* and PP947751 for *Schizophyllum commune*). The optimum growth conditions of the fungal mycelia and fungal biomass inoculated with metal ions were found at a temperature of 28 ± 2 °C and pH 6. The fungal strains exhibited growth up to a maximum concentration of 500 mg/L for Pb(II), Sr(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II). However, the growth of fungal biomass decreased with increasing metal concentration, and no growth was observed at concentrations above 500 mg/L. The fungal biomass was harvested after 7 days of incubation with metal ions using Whatman filter paper No. 4 (20 to 25 μ m). Later, the biomass was repeatedly washed with distilled water and kept at -80 °C for further antioxidant enzyme estimations.

Protein estimation

Protein estimation was performed following Lowry's method using BSA as a standard. The total protein content of the biomass before and after accumulating metal ions is shown in Fig. 1. The total protein of untreated biomass was observed as 0.080 ± 0.004 mg/ml for *C. striatus* and 0.011 ± 0.0005 mg/ml for *S. commune*. In *C. striatus*, the protein content increased to 4-fold at an initial concentration of metal ions, and later it decreased with higher concentrations. The maximum protein content was observed as 0.350 ± 0.019 mg/ml after exposure to 100 mg/L Pb(II), and the minimum was observed as 0.037 ± 0.010 mg/ml after

exposure to 500 mg/L Sr(II) in *C. striatus*. Whereas the highest protein content was 0.219 ± 0.010 mg/ml after accumulating 200 mg/L Zn(II), and the lowest was observed as 0.011 ± 0.0008 mg/ml after accumulating 100 mg/L Pb(II) in *S. commune*. The protein content in *S. commune* after accumulating Pb(II) was comparatively lower than that of other metal ions, which indicates that Pb(II) might have little influence on total protein content.

Malonaldehyde estimation

The MDA content, as the end product of lipid peroxidation, was estimated to measure the oxidative damage after accumulation of metal ions. The MDA content of the untreated biomass of *C. striatus* and *S. commune* was 0.765 ± 0.090 and 0.782 ± 0.157 μ M/g, respectively. The MDA content was significantly increased at a metal ion concentration of 100 mg/L and later decreased at higher concentrations (Fig. 2). In *C. striatus*, the maximum MDA content was observed as 3.458 ± 0.201 μ M/g after exposure to 100 mg/L Sr(II), and the minimum was observed as 0.653 ± 0.039 μ M/g after exposure to 500 mg/L Cd(II). In case of *S. commune*, the highest MDA content was 3.483 ± 0.271 μ M/g after exposure to 100 mg/L Cd(II), and the lowest was 1.075 ± 0.208 μ M/g after exposure to 500 mg/L Cd(II). For both fungal strains, it was observed that the MDA concentration was highest at the lowest concentration of metal ions, and later it decreased at higher concentrations.

Figure 1. Effect of metal ion exposure on Protein content of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b). Malonaldehyde estimation.

Slika 1. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na vsebnost beljakovin v *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena malonaldehida.

Catalase estimation

The significance of oxidative stress in the alteration of the antioxidant enzymes (including CAT, POD, and SOD) was assessed by analysing the impact of treatment with different concentrations (100–500 mg/l) of the heavy metals. The significance of CAT as a key antioxidant defence in both fungal strains is evidenced by the increased CAT activity in response to heavy metals. The CAT activity of untreated biomass of *C. striatus* and *S. commune* was observed as 0.005 ± 0.0009 and 0.005 ± 0.002 U/L, respectively. However, the CAT activity increased with initial exposure

of 100 mg/L metal ions in both strains and decreased with higher metal ion concentrations (Fig. 3). In *C. striatus*, the maximum CAT activity was observed as 0.065 ± 0.002 U/L with exposure to 100 mg/L Pb(II), while the minimum activity was observed as 0.008 ± 0.0008 U/L with exposure to 500 mg/L Zn(II). In *S. commune*, on exposure to 300 mg/L Cd(II), the highest CAT activity (0.025 ± 0.002 U/L) was observed, and the lowest CAT activity (0.003 ± 0.0005 U/L) was observed at 500 mg/L Zn(II). In *S. commune*, the CAT activity increased nearly 5-fold at 400 mg/L of Cd(II); however, a sharp decline was observed at 500 mg/L Cd(II), reaching 0.012 ± 0.001 U/L.

Figure 2. Effect of metal ion exposure on MDA content of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b) Catalase estimation.

Slika 2. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na vsebnost MDA v *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena katalaze.

Figure 3. Effect of metal ion exposure on CAT activity of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b) Peroxidase estimation.

Slika 3. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na aktivnost CAT pri *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena peroksidaze.

Peroxidase estimation

The POD activity with exposure to heavy metals is shown in Fig. 4. The POD activity of untreated *C. striatus* and *S. commune* biomass was observed as 1.906 ± 0.654 U/L and 1.646 ± 0.270 U/L, respectively. Like CAT, the POD activity also significantly increased during the initial exposure to heavy metal (100 mg/L), which suggests that it might be an ROS scavenger in the antioxidant system. On exposure to 100 mg/L Zn(II), *C. striatus* showed the highest POD activity (32.63 ± 0.811 U/L), and the lowest (2.426 ± 1.916 U/L) was observed with exposure to 500 mg/L Cd(II). The POD activity of *C. striatus* on exposure to Cd(II) was comparatively lower than exposure to other metal ions, which indicates that Cd(II) might have little influence on POD. In case of *S. commune*, the maximum POD activity (6.500 ± 0.520 U/L) was observed with exposure to 100 mg/L Pb(II), and the lowest (1.950 ± 0.260 U/L) was observed for 500 mg/L Zn(II). The results revealed that changes in POD activity of *S. commune* were comparatively lower than those of *C. striatus* on exposure to metal ions.

Superoxide dismutase estimation

The SOD activity, like CAT and POD, also increased on exposure to metal ions and decreased at higher metal concentrations. The SOD activity of untreated *C. striatus* and *S. commune* biomass was 0.009 ± 0.0009 and 0.011 ± 0.0006

U/mg, respectively. At an initial concentration of metal ions (100 mg/L), the SOD activity significantly increased in both strains. In *C. striatus*, the SOD activity reached its maximum value (0.054 ± 0.005 and 0.054 ± 0.002 U/mg) on exposure to 300 mg/L Zn(II) and 400 mg/L Pb(II), while the lowest activity (0.014 ± 0.003 U/mg) was observed at 500 mg/L Zn(II). In *S. commune*, SOD reached its maximum activity (0.062 ± 0.0007 U/mg) on exposure to 400 mg/L Sr(II), and the lowest activity (0.015 ± 0.003 U/mg) was observed after exposure to 500 mg/L Pb(II), as shown in Fig. 5.

Glutathione estimation

The GSH activity with exposure to heavy metals is shown in Fig. 6. The GSH activity of untreated *C. striatus* and *S. commune* biomass was observed as 7.896 ± 1.002 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 7.303 ± 0.559 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The highest GSH concentration (69.229 ± 1.050 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed on exposure to 100 mg/L Zn(II), and the lowest (17.155 ± 1.237 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed on exposure to 500 mg/L Pb(II) in *C. striatus*. The GSH content increased with an increase in concentration of Sr(II) and Cd(II) in *C. striatus*. In case of *S. commune*, the highest GSH content (93.674 ± 1.667 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed for 100 mg/L Cd(II), and the lowest (12.044 ± 1.175 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed for 500 mg/L Pb(II). In *S. commune*, except for Sr(II), the GSH content decreased with an increase in metal ion concentration.

The detailed numerical data for all the enzymatic activity measurements are provided in Table S1.

Figure 4. Effect of metal ion exposure on POD activity of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b). Superoxide dismutase estimation.

Slika 4. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na aktivnost POD pri *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena superoksid dismutaze.

Figure 5. Effect of metal ion exposure on SOD activity of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b). Glutathione estimation.

Slika 5. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na aktivnost SOD pri *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) Ocena glutationa.

Figure 6. Effect of metal ion exposure on GSH content of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b).

Slika 6. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na vsebnost GSH v *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b)

Discussion

Mycoremediation using Basidiomycota fungi nowadays offers a promising approach for treating water contaminated with heavy metals due to their high biomass production, strong metal binding capacity, and efficient enzymatic systems (Zare et al., 2024). Cell walls of lignicolous fungi are rich in functional groups, such as amino, carboxyl, hydroxyl, and phosphate groups, which facilitate the adsorption and accumulation of metal ions (Mondal et al., 2024b; 2025). Furthermore, effective colonization

and metal immobilization in aquatic environments are facilitated by their extensive hyphal networks and ability to grow on lignocellulosic substrates. These fungi typically use two mechanisms to remove heavy metals from liquid cultures: intracellular bioaccumulation and extracellular adsorption. The biosorption processes often include surface adsorption by ion-exchange, surface precipitation, and hydrolytic adsorption, which make it easier for ions to pass through the cell wall and membrane (Mondal et al., 2024a). However, when metal ions enter the cell, they disrupt the cellular redox homeostasis, which starts the

production of ROS, and subsequently leads to oxidative stress. Excessive ROS might cause harmful effects on cells and cause functional changes in protein and lipid peroxidation (Berni et al., 2019). Nonetheless, the antioxidant system of fungi aids in scavenging excessive ROS through coordinated enzymatic and non-enzymatic defences, thereby preventing ROS accumulation and maintaining cellular redox homeostasis. In response to heavy metal stress, fungal biomass ensures a balanced antioxidative system by producing enzymatic antioxidants, like CAT, POD, SOD, and non-enzymatic antioxidants, like GSH, and protects its cellular components (Li et al., 2020).

In this study, the ability of two selected wild strains of lignicolous fungi, *Cyathus striatus* and *Schizophyllum commune*, was investigated to grow in liquid media containing different concentrations (100-500 mg/L) of metal ions. The selected strains showed tolerance to metal ions, including Pb(II), Sr(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) up to a concentration of 500 mg/L. The metal uptake capacity of live biomass of *C. striatus* and *S. commune* was earlier reported as 65.55, 56.15, 71.33, and 65.94 mg/g and 81.5, 90.71, 70.18, 66.18 mg/g, and for Pb(II), Sr(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II), respectively (Mondal et al., 2024b; Mondal et al., 2025). In this study, the protein content of the fungal mycelium was significantly higher at lower concentrations of metal ions, which might be attributed to metal-protein interactions and initial adaptive response to metal exposure (Kalsoom et al., 2023). However, a relative decrease in protein content was observed with increased metal concentration, indicating ROS-induced oxidative stress and possible protein oxidation or degradation. Similar findings were observed for *Sclerotium rolfsii* (Rafi et al., 2017) and *Talaromyces pinophilus* (Dwivedi, 2023). Additionally, the important antioxidant enzymes, including CAT, POD, SOD, and their responses to different concentrations of metal ions, were also examined. The three antioxidant enzymes exhibit different responses to exposure to metal ions. Increased concentrations of metal ions generate more free radicals in *S. striatus* and *C. commune*, which creates strong oxidising conditions *in vivo*. We found that CAT activity suddenly increased at 100 mg/L concentration of metal ions and decreased at higher concentrations, suggesting that metal ions induce H₂O₂ accumulation and cause oxidative damage. Similar results were reported in *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* for the removal of Cd(II) and *Pleurotus ostreatus* for the tolerance of Pb(II) (Zhang et al., 2015; 2016). Similarly, the POD activity also increased with exposure to metal ions and later

decreased at higher concentrations. However, the activity of CAT was comparatively lower than POD activity under identical conditions for both fungal strains. The inhibition of CAT and POD at higher concentrations of metal ions may be due to enhanced production of H₂O₂, which eventually suppresses the CAT and POD activity (Sidhu et al., 2016).

SOD is also one of the antioxidant enzymes that protects the cells from both internal and external ROS in all aerobic species (Ozougwu, 2016). SOD catalyses the dismutation of O₂⁻, O₂, and H₂O₂, which is later reduced by CAT and POD. In this study, the SOD activity also increased with metal ion concentrations and further decreased at higher concentrations. Increased SOD activity could be due to the direct effect of heavy metal ions or an indirect effect mediated by an increase in superoxide radical levels and the *de novo* synthesis of enzyme proteins (Dhalaria et al., 2020). The upregulation of SOD during the metal ion exposure enhances the dismutation of O₂⁻ into less reactive species, thereby reducing the oxidative stress. Consistent with the findings, *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Aspergillus oryzae* were reported to show similar results during oxidative stress induced by Pb(II) and Cu(II), respectively (Zhang et al., 2016; Long et al., 2017). Also, *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* showed similar results for the accumulation of Pb(II) (Huang et al., 2017).

On exposure to metal ions, the phospholipid bilayers of cell membranes are vulnerable to ROS oxidation, which results in lipid peroxidation (El-Mahdy et al., 2021). MDA, which is a major byproduct of lipid peroxidation, acts as a biomarker of oxidative stress. In this study, MDA showed the extent of ROS-induced membrane damage, which also increased drastically at the initial concentration (100 mg/L) of metal ions in both fungal strains. However, the MDA concentration gradually decreased with an increase in the concentration of metal ions up to 500 mg/L. This may be attributed to an initial increase in lipid peroxidation caused by elevated ROS generation at moderate metal exposure. At higher metal concentrations, enhanced activation of antioxidant defence mechanisms and reduced metabolic activity may limit the ROS production and membrane lipid oxidation, resulting in lower MDA levels (Luo et al., 2022). Similar results were reported under Cd and Cu stress in an ectomycorrhizal fungus, *Lepista sordida* (Dachuan and Jinyu, 2021) and in *Pleurotus ostreatus* HAU-2 for accumulation of Pb(II) (Zhang et al., 2016).

The detoxification of non-essential heavy metals often occurs by the synthesis of low molecular weight chelators, like GSH. Heavy metal exposure, oxidative stress, and lack

of sulphur or nitrogen are among the stress factors that influence this process (Huang et al., 2017). GSH accumulation is impeded by prolonged and excessive exposure to heavy metals, most likely because of the possible toxicity of heavy metals to microorganisms. GSH, a significant non-enzymatic antioxidant, was evaluated at varying concentrations of metal ions. Results showed that GSH activity increased with 100 mg/L metal ion concentration in both strains. However, in *C. striatus*, it was observed that with an increase in metal ion concentration, the GSH activity decreased when exposed to Pb(II) and Zn(II) and increased when exposed to Sr(II) and Cd(II). The decrease in GSH activity at higher concentrations of metal ions confirmed that the metal ions induce ROS production (Gulcin and Alwasel, 2022). Similarly, in *S. commune*, with an increase in metal ion concentration, the GSH activity decreased for Pb(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) and increased in the case of Sr(II). These variations in results might be due to the excessive exposure to metal ions, which decreased the GSH level, probably due to excessive utilisation in ROS scavenging (Mansoor et al., 2023). In some cases, the GSH synthesis is upregulated with an increase in metal ion concentration via the γ -glutamyl cycle to detoxify the metal ions (Georgiou-Siafis and Tsiftoglou, 2023). Additionally, metal ions reduce the availability of sulfhydryl groups or other functional groups that are bound to proteins and can substitute for cofactors necessary for enzyme functions. This makes these enzymatic antioxidants vulnerable to metal-induced inactivation, which increases the production of ROS like H_2O_2 , hydroxyl radicals, and the superoxide species (Khullar and Sudhakara Reddy, 2019). At higher metal ion concentrations, the gradual accumulation of GSSG was observed, which suggests that GSH could react with H_2O_2 to produce GSSG, catalysed by glutathione peroxidase. Similar results were observed for the accumulation of Pb(II) in *P. ostreatus* (Zhang et al., 2016) and in *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* (Xu et al., 2014). Furthermore, heavy metals can be sequestered and detoxified by the GSH-dependent synthesis of metal-binding peptides, such as phytochelatins, which increases GSH depletion by producing persistent GSH-metal complexes intracellularly (Huang et al., 2017).

Conclusion

In the present work, *C. striatus* and *S. commune* were investigated for their tolerance and oxidative stress response

to heavy metal stress. *S. commune* and *C. striatus* both showed a high level of heavy metal tolerance and were able to endure up to 500 mg/L. Upon exposure to heavy metals, the intracellular accumulation of H_2O_2 increased, which triggered lipid peroxidation and subsequent MDA production. Heavy metal exposure significantly altered the activity of enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants, reflecting an induced cellular stress response that protects the cells against ROS. An increase in protein content and activity of antioxidant enzymes, including CAT, POD, and SOD, at the initial exposure to metal ions suggests a coordinated defence response to counteract metal-induced oxidative stress. Additionally, the GSH also plays an important role in the detoxification of metal ions, indicating its involvement in maintaining intracellular redox balance. However, at higher metal concentrations, a decline in CAT, POD, SOD, and GSH activity was observed, likely due to excessive ROS generation surpassing the antioxidant defence system. Overall, the results showed that heavy metal exposure adversely affects fungal cellular physiology while simultaneously triggering robust antioxidant defence mechanisms. The negative impacts of oxidative stress are avoided by the induced enzymatic antioxidants, including SOD, POD, and CAT. Thus, the Basidiomycota fungi, *C. striatus* and *S. commune*, exhibited pronounced antioxidant defence responses under heavy metal exposure, reflecting their capacity to mitigate metal-induced oxidative stress and maintain cellular redox balance.

Author contributions

Writing-Original draft, P.M.; Data curation, P.M.; Validation, P.M.; Methodology, P.M.; Investigation, P.M.; Writing: Review and Editing, D.K.K.; Writing-Review and Editing, S.R.; Supervision, S.R.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Data availability statement

Research data is available at Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.18359581).

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